

The Influence of Leadership Style on Personnel Performance with Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable: Case of Police Personel in Jakarta

Rheza Kurnia Fajar¹, Basir S², Jerry Marcellinus Logahan³

Article history:

Received April, 29, 2022, Accepted: June, 25, 2022, Displayed Online: June, 30, 2022; Published: June, 30, 2022

Keywords

Abstract

Job Satisfaction;

Leadership Style;

Personel

Performance;

Police Officers;

The purpose of the current research is to analyzing the influence of the existing leadership style in the company on the performance of personnel, the existing leadership style in the company on job satisfaction, analyze the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of the personnel. The sample of this study were members of the Police Station in Lebak-Jakarta, Indonesia. The sampling technique in this study used non-probability sampling, and purposive sampling with data collection carried out by giving questionnaires. There are 125 questionnaires distributed, and 92 questionnaires can be used. The analytical technique used to analyze the data obtained is the Partial Least Square (PLS) technique using Smart PLS software. From the results of hypothesis testing, there are several conclusions in this study. Namely, there is a significant influence between Leadership Style on personnel performance. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted. There is a positive and significant influence between Leadership Style on job satisfaction. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 2 (H2) is accepted. There is a significant positive effect between job satisfaction on personnel performance. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted. Thus, job satisfaction can mediate Leadership Style on personnel performance. So it can be

¹Indonesia University, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: rhezakurniafajar02@gmail.com

²Indonesia University, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: basirsagena@gmail.com

³Indonesia University, Jakarta, Indonesia. Email: jerrymarcellinus59@gmail.com

concluded that Hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted. Thus, job satisfaction can mediate Leadership Style on personnel performance. So it can be concluded that Hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted. Thus, job satisfaction can mediate Leadership Style on personnel performance.

1. Introduction

Performance is the result of work, both in quality and quantity, achieved by a person carrying out tasks according to the responsibilities given (Mangkunegara, 2016). It relates to all or part of the actions of the organization's activities in a period concerning many standards such as projected past costs based on efficiency, accountability or management accountability, and the like in achieving its goals (Rivai, 2013). Performance is work performance, namely the comparison between work results and established standards (Dessler, 2015). Experts argue that performance is not only seen from the result but is seen from the performance process (Armstrong, 2016). According to Nawawi (2016), performance is high if a work target can be completed at the right time or does not exceed the time limit.

Personnel performance will then describe how the personnel/members do their work from time to time and show how much a person or employee can do their job and is full of responsibility. This is then used to measure the organization's success level in achieving its goals. Because of the importance of employee performance in measuring organizational productivity, various studies review the factors that can affect personnel performance. Leadership style is one of the factors reviewed among the various factors that can affect the performance of personnel. Leadership style is considered to improve individual performance in organizations, which includes influencing in determining organizational goals, motivating follower behavior to achieve goals, and influencing to improve the group and culture (Rivai and Mulyadi, 2016). Leadership is sometimes understood as the power to move and influence people. Leadership as a tool, means, or process to persuade people to be willing to do something voluntarily / joy, The fashion/type/style of leadership put forward by the authors is different. However, its meaning and essence are aimed at encouraging work passion, decisions, and high employee productivity to achieve maximum organizational goals.

Rivai (2016) says leadership style is a set of characteristics leaders possess to influence their subordinates, and the organizational goals can be achieved. According to Nawawi (2013), leadership style is the behavior or method chosen and used by the leader in influencing the thoughts, feelings, attitudes, and behavior of members of the organization or subordinates. Maulizar et al. (2013) leadership describe the relationship between the leader (leader) and those who are led (followers) and determine the extent to which the leader achieves the goals or expectations of the leader.

But then, research on the relationship between leadership style and personnel performance until now still shows various things. However, most studies show a relationship between leadership style and personnel performance Tian & Sanchez (2017). However, some studies have the opposite findings. Dolly & Nonyelum (2018) found that leadership style significantly negatively affects

personnel performance. This leadership style tends to have less productive workgroups, and subordinates are highly dissatisfied with their work.

Based on this review, the purpose of this study is to conduct a conceptual review of the existing research literature by comparing the research findings and then gaining a thorough understanding of the relationship between leadership style and personnel performance. This research will contribute to developing insight into the relationship between leadership style and personnel performance and provide a conceptual framework that can be used for further research development.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Personnel Performance

Performance describes the amount of work an individual can complete in a certain time. Performance can be considered as a description of the level of achievement of the implementation of a program of activities or policies that impact the organization's goals, vision, and mission through the strategic planning organization (Shilpa, 2015). Performance is a general term used in part or all of the actions or activities of an organization over a period concerning several standards such as projected past costs based on efficiency, management responsibility or accountability, and the like (Rivai, 2013).

There are several performance measures related to the criteria Performance of personnel according to the Regulation of the National Police Chief No. 11 of 2012 concerning Preparation of Performance Determination within the Indonesian National Police Measurements of Member Performance, are:

1. Leadership, with indicators: Able to motivate fellow members at the work unit level, Ability to direct at the work unit level.
2. Service Orientation, with indicators: Ability to manage the service orientation process at the work unit level and evaluate at the work unit level.
3. Communication, with indicators: Coordination in completing tasks according to procedures, Communication between management lines within the agency.
4. Emotional control, with indicators: Ability to control emotions and put oneself in various situations.
5. Integrity, with indicators: Completing tasks effectively, Ability to complete tasks in accordance with organizational targets
6. Empathy, with indicators: Ability to place oneself and express feelings towards performance. x
7. Commitment to the organization, with indicators: where the employee has a commitment to work with the agency and the employee's responsibility to the office.
8. The initiative, with indicators: Able to overcome the problems encountered, Have knowledge and skills at the work unit level.
9. Discipline, with indicators: Discipline in completing tasks effectively, Ability to complete tasks in accordance with organizational targets.

10. Cooperation, with indicators: Ability to maintain and work together at the work unit level, Cooperation at the work unit level.

According to Inuwa (2016), Performance measurement uses an instrument that describes the overall meaning of the performance itself, and the instrument is also short enough to speed up the data collection process. Based on the description above, it is synthesized that personnel performance is a management process for assessing the level of achievement of performance indicators, which compares performance targets with performance realization.

2.2 Leadership Style

Leadership style is a pattern of behavior designed in such a way as to integrate organizational goals with individual goals to achieve a certain goal (Suzy, 2016). Leadership style can be defined as a pattern of behavior designed to integrate organizational goals with individual goals to achieve a certain goal (Heidjrachman and Husnan, 2012).

Rivai (2016) says leadership style is a set of characteristics leaders possess to influence their subordinates for organizational goals to be achieved. According to Nawawi (2013), leadership style is the behavior or method chosen and used by the leader in influencing the thoughts, feelings, attitudes, and behavior of members of the organization or subordinates. Maulizar et al. (2013) leadership describe the relationship between the leader (leader) and those who are led (followers) and determine the extent to which the leader achieves the goals or expectations of the leader. Leadership plays an important role in an organization because the manager moves and guides the organization to achieve the desired goals. According to Sutikno (2014), the characteristics or indicators of leadership are:

1. In centralized decision-making, an executive with this authoritarian style feels the privilege and privilege of his subordinates. The decision-making process only focuses on leadership. In other words, employees are not given all the rights determined by the manager and are not part of the decision-making process. Employees are only obligated and responsible for carrying out managerial decisions and orders.
2. Tasks are described in detail. That is, what managers inform about employee behavior must be in accordance with the wishes of the manager.
3. The subjectivity of the leader when dealing with subordinates, the leader includes his personal feelings. As with assessing an employee's work, the leader only considers their personal feelings. This rating is based on his preference for employees.
4. The opinion is a mere verbal service. In this case, the leadership does not give employees the actual opportunity to participate in opinions, suggestions, etc., because all decisions are made solely by the leadership.

5. With strict supervision, the leader monitors all his subordinates. During work, regardless of whether the process meets the standards set by the company, this affects each employee's workspace and is excessive by the manager. Supervision puts employees under pressure.

2.3 Job Satisfaction

Donni (2017) defines job satisfaction as a set of feelings of members/personnel towards their work, whether happy / like or not happy / dislike as a result of the interaction of members/personnel with their work environment or as a perception of mental attitudes, also as a result of the assessment of members/personnel towards their work. Feelings of members/personnel towards their work reflect their attitudes and behavior at work. Meanwhile, according to Handoko (2015), Job satisfaction is a pleasant or unpleasant emotional state with the extent to which members/personnel view their work.

Vroom, as quoted by Ahmad, MA Roshidi (1999), defines job satisfaction as a reference to an employee's effective orientation towards their role in his current position. A positive attitude towards work can conceptually be expressed as job satisfaction, and a negative attitude towards work equals dissatisfaction. This definition has received support from Smith and Kendall (1963), who explained that job satisfaction is an employee's feelings about his job. According to Celluci, Anthony J. and David L. DeVries (1978) in Fuad Mas'ud (2004), job satisfaction can be measured by the following indicators:

1. Satisfaction of salary
2. Satisfaction of promotion
3. Satisfaction of co-workers
4. Satisfaction of supervisor
5. Satisfaction of the work itself

2.4 Leadership Style and Job Satisfaction

One study by Byco et al. (1985) suggests that leadership style significantly affects job satisfaction. It is also supported by Andri Budiman (2003) research that the transformational leadership style is more influential than the transactional leadership style on job satisfaction. The right leadership style is oriented toward creating job satisfaction. With the right leadership style, members/personnel will respect their work and be willing to contribute their best. With job satisfaction, subordinates will respond to various aspects of their work pleasantly, which is the essence of job satisfaction. Although motivation is abstract, leaders also need to understand the motivations of their subordinates. Understanding the motivation of their subordinates will be important for leaders to be able to direct them to be able to obtain job satisfaction because job satisfaction that can be achieved will support employee work productivity.

2.5 Leadership Style and Personnel Performance

There are various studies that have conducted a review of the relationship between leadership style and employee performance. Robins (2016) said that leaders who inspire followers to do things beyond their personal interests for the company's sake can have a profound and extraordinary impact on personnel. Previous studies have examined the effect of leadership style on performance and proved that leadership style positively affects performance.

Torlak & Kuzey (2019) and Tian & Sanchez (2017) found that leadership style is a variable that positively influences performance. Meanwhile, Dolly & Nonyelum (2018) and Jameel & Ahmad (2020) found that leadership in police personnel was a factor that significantly improved personnel performance.

Research conducted by Pawirosumarto et al. (2017), Buil et al. (2018), Lor & Hassan (2017), and Basit et al. (2018) document that leadership style has a positive and significant influence on personnel performance. Contrary to the results of research by Malcalm & Tamatey (2017), Tobing & Syaiful (2018), Ridlwan et al. (2021), and Rafia et al. (2020) said there was no significant effect of leadership style on performance.

2.6 Job Satisfaction and Personnel Performance

According to Wibowo (2016), it is revealed that personnel who are satisfied with their work have a positive impact on the achievements obtained from the achievement of one's work. Job satisfaction has five important indicators, namely the first salary. This study shows that many employees agree that salary is important because the salary or rewards obtained will determine whether an employee is more enthusiastic at work. Therefore salary is a measure where employee performance will be maximized.

Previous research on job satisfaction on performance has been conducted by Ridlwan et al. (2021), and Rafia et al. (2020), which produces job satisfaction has a positive effect on the performance of members/personnel. Furthermore, research conducted by Fadlalh (2015) and Ali & Farooqi (2014) found that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the performance of members/personnel.

2.7 Leadership Style on Personnel Performance with Job Satisfaction

Utami (2014) revealed that a good leader always motivates his subordinates. Thus, it can have a positive impact on the achievements obtained from the achievement of one's work. Previous research on leadership on performance has been conducted by Rafia et al. (2020), which results in leadership having a positive effect on the performance of members/personnel through job satisfaction, while the research of Pawirosumarto et al. (2017) says there is no influence of leadership style on personnel performance through job satisfaction. Good performance is generally a result of job satisfaction felt by individuals. Job satisfaction arises from internal and external factors.

This study predicted external factors in a latent construct of leadership, while internal factors were predicted from leadership style. Wibowo (2016) revealed that members/personnel who are satisfied with their work positively impact the achievements obtained from one's work. Leadership and job satisfaction have a very strong influence on the significant impact on the performance of members/personnel. This indicates that leadership and job satisfaction effectively influence efforts to improve the performance of members/personnel of regional companies.

2.8 Research methods

This research is quantitative research. Data collection techniques focus on collecting data in the form of numbers with the purpose that evidence can be presented in quantitative form. Therefore, this research was conducted conceptually on previous research related to Leadership Style on the performance of personnel members with job satisfaction as an intervening variable. The literature that is used as a reference in this study is limited to a span of ten years.

3. Result and Discussion

The results of this study can be assessed by looking at the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. In general, the results showed that a review of the relationship between leadership style and personnel performance with job satisfaction as an intervening variable was carried out using quantitative methods.

Based on the results of the study, the influence between authoritarian leadership style and personnel performance. The authoritarian leadership style significantly affects personnel performance because it has a probability value of 0.000 (0.0 %) which is < 5%, with a coefficient of 0.422 which means H1 is accepted. The results of research related to authoritarian Leadership Style and its impact on personnel performance are also similar to research by K. et al. (2020) entitled "The impact of leadership on firm financial performance: the mediating role of employees' "readiness to change" shows the importance of leadership in driving company performance.

Then, the authoritarian leadership style has an effect on job satisfaction because it has a probability value of 0.000 (0.0%) which is < 5%, with a coefficient of 0.885, meaning that H2 is accepted. Analysis result of Hassan et al. (2017) and Ridlwani et al. (2021) shows that the leadership style has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction, which means that the better the local leadership, the satisfaction of members/personnel will increase.

There are several studies that conclude that leadership style affects the performance of members/personnel. Rosnani's research (2012) shows that leadership has a significant positive effect on performance, and leadership has a positive but not significant effect on performance. Research by Paracha et al. (2012) shows that leadership has a positive effect on the performance of members/personnel, and leadership has a positive but weak effect on the performance of members/personnel. Komba (2013) showed a positive and significant effect on the performance of members/personnel.

Followed by the next variable, Job Satisfaction has an effect on the Performance of Personnel / Members because it has a probability value of 0.000 (0.0 %) and is < 5%, so H3 is accepted. Similar research related to Job Satisfaction and also its influence on the Performance of Personnel / Members have also been studied previously, previous research conducted by Previous research on job

satisfaction on performance has been conducted by Ridlwan et al. (2021) and Rafia et al. (2020), which produces job satisfaction has a positive effect on the performance of members/personnel. Furthermore, research conducted by Fadlalh (2015) and Ali & Farooqi (2014) found that job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on the performance of members/personnel. Job satisfaction is an emotional attitude that is pleasant and loves his job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work performance. Job satisfaction is enjoyed at work, outside work, and a combination of inside and outside work (Hasibuan, 2013). According to research conducted by Rosnani (2012), job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on the performance of members/personnel. It is evident from research conducted by Memesah and Kusmaningtyas (2009) that job satisfaction has a significant positive effect on the performance of members/personnel.

4. Conclusion

There are several conclusions based on the discussion of the research findings that have been carried out. The existing leadership style variable on performance has a greater value if it is mediated by job satisfaction. This means that in an effort to improve the performance of personnel/members in an organization, a good Leadership Style variable through Job Satisfaction has a greater role because the value of the Leadership Style variable mediated by the Job Satisfaction variable on the performance of members/personnel has a higher value when compared with the value of the Leadership Style variable without being mediated through Job Satisfaction. Moreover, when viewed from the leadership style that inspires, always instills a sense of pride and confidence, putting aside personal and other interests can actually increase their sense of satisfaction, which also impacts their performance. With a good leadership style can also have a good influence on the performance of members / personnel.

From this explanation, it can be explained that if the leader is authoritarian, job satisfaction and personnel performance will decrease because from the data that has been examined the results if the leader has good character and can understand his subordinates will make a major contribution to his members and materialize job satisfaction and good personnel performance. good, too.

Job satisfaction must also be maintained by organizations including the police organization, especially the Lebak POLRES (Police Station). As it is known that in addition to mediating the research variables, job satisfaction also directly influences the performance of members/personnel. Furthermore, the results in this study also provide managerial implications for the object of research, namely the Lebak Police, to improve the performance of personnel/members, it can be achieved by improving aspects of leadership style and job satisfaction. With the leadership style in an organization, job satisfaction and personnel performance is likely to decrease because of the data that has been examined the results if the leader has good character and can understand his subordinates will make a major contribution to his members and realize job satisfaction and personnel performance. A good one also turns out to be able to improve the performance of personnel/members. Likewise, the mediating effect of Job Satisfaction also improved the performance of personnel/members.

Thus, the organization must be able to maintain these aspects in order to improve the performance of its members/personnel. The company can do it by always observing how the

Leadership Style is like strengthening the relationship between members / personnel by instilling pride in members, not going beyond interests, having self-confidence and inspiring. That way it will create job satisfaction for good personnel / members. Furthermore, to maintain and improve the performance of personnel/members in the organization, it is to increase the attitude of job satisfaction, such as paying attention to needs that can increase the satisfaction of personnel/members at work.

From the results of the study, it is also known that the Leadership Style variable mediated by the variable Job satisfaction is stronger in dominating efforts to improve the performance of personnel/members. Furthermore, it can be a concern for the object of research in an effort to improve the performance of the personnel/members. Furthermore, it is hoped that future research is expected to conduct research using other variables related to the performance of personnel/members in organizations or companies, for example, work climate, readiness for change, work motivation, and others. Thus, it can later be able to provide a broader picture of what factors can affect the performance of personnel/members other than Leadership Style and Job Satisfaction.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to express their deepest gratitude to the publisher, TIJOSSW, who has given permission and a great opportunity for publishing the current manuscript. Further appreciation is delivered to the reviewers of the TIJOSSW publisher, who have taken more time to make valuable corrections regarding the technical writing style or ideas of this manuscript.

References

- Abubakr, S., & Bader, A. H. (2013). Perceived Work Climate And Employee Performance In Public Security Organizations In The Uae. *Transforming Government: People, Process And Policy*, 7(3), 410–424. <https://doi.org/10.1108/Tg-03-2012-0001>
- Agni Devi, S., & Megawati, S. (N.D.). *Analisa Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Otoriter Dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Departemen Room Division Swiss-Belinn Hotel Manyar Surabaya*. (2011), 529–545.
- Buil, I., Martínez, E., & Matute, J. (2018). Transformational Leadership And Employee Performance: The Role Of Identification, Engagement And Proactive Personality. *International Journal Of Hospitality Management*, 77(June 2018), 64–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.06.014>
- Dolly C, K., & Nonyelum P., O. (2018). Impact Of Democratic Leadership Style On Job Performance Of Subordinates In Academic Libraries In Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal Of Research -Granthaalayah*, 6(10), 232–239. <https://doi.org/10.29121/Granthaalayah.V6.I10.2018.1190>
- Fenwick, F. J., C., A. G., & Harald, B. (2011). Organizational Climate And Performance In Retail Pharmacies. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 32(3), 224–242. <https://doi.org/10.1108/01437731111123898>
- Lor, W., & Hassan, Z. (2017). The Influence Of Leadership On Employee Performance Among Jewellery Artisans In Malaysia. *International Journal Of Accounting & Business Management*, 5(1), 14–33.
- Malcalm, E., & Tamatey, S. (2017). Examining Leadership Style On Employee Performance In The Public Sector Of Ghana. *International Journal Of Scientific And Research Publications*, 7(11), 343–361.
- Mangkunegara, A. P. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Perusahaan* (Susan Sandiasih, Ed.).
- Mutonyi, B. R., Slåtten, T., & Lien, G. (2020). Organizational Climate And Creative Performance In The Public Sector. *European Business Review*, 32(4), 615–631. <https://doi.org/10.1108/Ebr-02-2019-0021>
- Nurhamiden, R. K., & Trang, I. (2015). *Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan, Komunikasi, Dan Pembagian Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Polisi Pada Polda Sulut Manado*. 3(3), 971–980.
- Pt, K., Paramita, A., & Tbk, I. (2018). *Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Otoriter, Komunikasi Organisasi, Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pt. Asia Paramita Indah Tbk. Mandom Di Surakarta*.
- Rivai, V. (2013). *Kepemimpinan Dan Perilaku Organisasi (Ketiga)*.
- Shilpa, W. (2015). *The International Journal Of Business & Management Impact Of Effective Employee Performance Management On Organizational*. 3(11), 183–196.
- Tian, Q., & Sanchez, J. I. (2017). Does Paternalistic Leadership Promote Innovative Behavior? The Interaction Between Authoritarianism And Benevolence. *Journal Of Applied Social Psychology*, 47(5), 235–246. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jasp.12431>
- Torlak, N. G., & Kuzey, C. (2019). Leadership, Job Satisfaction And Performance Links In Private Education Institutes Of Pakistan. *International Journal Of Productivity And Performance Management*, 68(2), 276–295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/Ijppm-05-2018-0182>
- Utami, W. (2017). *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Gaya Kepemimpinan Dan Stres Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Anggota Polri. Studi Kasus Pada Kepolisian Sektor Lendah*.
- Wahid Rosyidi, A. (2013). *Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Terhadap Kinerja Pustakawan Pada Perpustakaan Perguruan Tinggi Negeri Di Surabaya*. (071016049).